

Verification and Validation of FVM-based Neutronic Solvers against TRIGA Mark II Reactor

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ABSTRACT

When developing new numerical solvers and codes, validation is a fundamental step before their practical applications, to determine the accuracy and reliable predictive capability. This work represents the first milestone towards the development of a dedicated multi-physics solver for the TRIGA Mark II family of research reactors, which serve as an invaluable benchmark for the nuclear world due to the availability of experimental data and the small dimensions, which allow full-scale modelling at a relatively low computational cost. To this end, two deterministic neutronics OpenFOAM solvers, one based on diffusion theory and the other on the Simplified Spherical Harmonics (SP3) approximation, have been tested against the TRIGA Mark II reactor. At first, the OpenMC code was used to calculate the cross-sections and provide a reference solution. In OpenFOAM, instead, a pin-by-pin core was built. For both verification and validation, the calibration curves and control rod worths for REG, SHIM, and TRANS, as well as the core excess reactivity, were calculated. The results show good agreement with both the available experimental measurements and the OpenMC reference, and the advantage of the SP3 solver to capture anisotropic effects is only observed in the SHIM rod reactivity worth and in the fully-inserted state of the calibration curves for both SHIM and TRANS. Regardless, the results demonstrate that both approximations can be used for the multi-physics model of the TRIGA Mark II reactor, as well as for practical applications.

Keywords: Validation; Diffusion Theory; SP3 Approximation; TRIGA Reactor; Calibration Curves

1. INTRODUCTION

In the nuclear field, the Monte Carlo (MC) method is well known for its high accuracy and outstanding capability in handling irregular geometries. However, for engineering-level applications, the computational cost remains a major challenge, making the expensive MC method not practical; additionally, time-dependent MC methods are still under development, whereas quasi-static approximations and hybrid deterministic MC methods may limit the temporal resolution. When shifting to Multi-Physics (MP) problems and coupling, mainly with thermal-hydraulics solvers, more issues arise (scale mismatch, cross-section feedback, even larger computational costs, convergence instability, uncertainty quantification, and so on), leading to a parallel research direction focusing on deterministic neutronics approaches and their coupling with thermal-hydraulics and other physics.

Among the available MP solvers for nuclear applications, the GeN-Foam library, which includes neutronics, thermal-hydraulics, and thermo-mechanics, is perhaps the most mature library [1]. Written in

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OpenFOAM with a focus on coarse-mesh (porous media), and developed by Fiorina et al., the neutronics module of GeN-Foam includes a solver based on diffusion [1], which was applied successfully to the full-core KIWI-B-4E nuclear thermal propulsion system [2], and a solver based on the Simplified Spherical Harmonics (SP3) approximation, which was validated against a mini-core PWR benchmark and then applied on the CROCUS experimental reactor [3]. Compared to diffusion-based calculations, the results show that the SP3 method achieved better performance in predicting flux distributions [3].

Other works include a 3D discrete ordinates neutronics and thermal-mechanics solver, capable of capturing the dynamic expansion effect in the Godiva spherical assembly [4]; a multi-region diffusion-based neutronics solver coupled with a conjugate heat transfer thermal-hydraulics solver, featuring a dedicated interface to ensure consistency across different regions, and validated against a 5×5 PWR assembly [5]; an SP3 neutronics solver with approximate Marshak boundary conditions based on OpenFOAM and validated against the ISSA pin-by-pin lattice and simplified core neutron transport benchmarks [6]. The above applications underline the capabilities of the open-source OpenFOAM platform for developing and validating solvers for nuclear applications. While GeN-FOAM is already capable of coupling multiple fields, its thermal-hydraulic part relies on a porous media module [1]. As such, it cannot directly handle the computational domains that include both fluid and solid regions. In addition, GeN-FOAM employs different meshes for different fields, making data mapping between them mandatory and significantly increasing the computational cost. Therefore, a high-resolution and single-mesh coupling tool is desired. In the broader context of MP solvers for nuclear applications, it is useful to validate each single-physics sub-module to verify not only their accuracy but also their correct implementation. Additionally, it is good practice to provide future users with different options for modeling their specific problems, such as different approximation levels for the various physics: for instance, considering neutronics, some reactors may be well described by a diffusion approach, whereas for others, a more high-fidelity approximation of the transport equation may be sought.

To this end, this work represents the first milestone in an ongoing project of developing a dedicated high-fidelity multi-physics solver for the TRIGA Mark II family of research reactors, based on OpenFOAM. Given its limited dimensions, this reactor allows focusing on high-fidelity solvers at a still reasonable computational cost, allowing the generation of a large enough database of cases for Machine Learning applications. Additionally, TRIGA reactors represent valuable validation tools: most existing neutronics solvers have been validated mostly against simple benchmark problems or highly simplified reactor cores; potentially, TRIGA reactors allow validation against a complete reactor model, which better reflects practical nuclear applications, and which is a fundamental step towards the licensing of new solvers for nuclear applications. Therefore, the relevance of this study also lies in the validation of the OpenFOAM-based diffusion and SP3 solvers against a high-fidelity and fully-featured model of the TRIGA Mark II reactor at the University of Pavia, Italy. Additionally, experimental data for research reactors are more easily shared with the research community, allowing for a more complete validation. As such, this work presents the validation of the OpenFOAM-based diffusion and SP3 neutronics solvers against the TRIGA Mark II reactor, focusing on reproducing the calibration curves, control rod worth, and core excess reactivity; additionally, verification is performed through comparison with OpenMC.

2. MODELING AND METHODOLOGY

The numerical tools for neutronic simulations are developed based on the open-source OpenFOAM v9 platform, which contains several consolidated libraries for nuclear applications. Considering the complexity of implementation and computational cost, this work begins with diffusion theory and is then extended to the SP3 approximation. The required cross-sections are obtained from the OpenMC code, and Python-based scripts are employed to convert the data structures to an OpenFOAM-suitable format and to prepare the boundary conditions. The geometry is discretized using Ansys Fluent Meshing.

2.1. Geometry Modelling

The TRIGA Mark II research reactors are designed for neutron activation analysis and educational training, and they represent a fundamental benchmark for the validation of numerical models for nuclear applications [7]. Briefly, TRIGA reactors consist of a core submerged in a water pool, with a total height of 6.85 m and a diameter of 1.98 m. For the TRIGA reactor at the University of Pavia, the core comprises 80 fuel rods, five graphite rods, three empty channels, and three control rods (CRs). The fuel is uranium zirconium hydride (UZrH) enriched to 20%, and two types of fuel elements are used: 50 of fuel-101 type (bounded at both ends by a samarium poison disk and a graphite cylinder, and enclosed in aluminum cladding) and 30 of fuel-103 type (enclosed in steel cladding, and without the Sm poison disk). The ZrH matrix provides a strong negative temperature reactivity coefficient. The three CRs are SHIM in the second ring, TRANS in the third ring, and REG in the fourth ring, as shown in Figure 1 in black (the center-most element correspond to ring 0, other rings are counted from the center moving towards the borders). The control rods serve mainly for emergency shutdown (TRANS) and for coarse (SHIM) and fine (REG) power regulation [8]. Figure 1 reports the OpenMC model for the TRIGA reactor, including both reactor core and pool.

Figure 1. The TRIGA reactor model; (a) top view of the entire model; (b) side view of the entire model; (c) top view of the core region; (d) side view of the core region; color legend: fuel-101 (pink), fuel-103 (brown), CRs (dark), graphite (green), air (dark green), cladding (peachy), water (blue). Other thin components are not clearly visible.

In OpenMC, the already built model includes detailed representations of the fuel pins, channels, reflector, the Lazy Susan (an irradiation facility), two grid plates, and the reactor pool. A comprehensive description of the model can be found in [7]. To obtain the relevant cross-sections, 6×10^5 particles were simulated over a total of 200 cycles, with the first 100 cycles discarded as inactive to ensure convergence of the fission source distribution. These settings achieve a relatively accurate result, with a relative error less than 2×10^{-4} for the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}).

Figure 2. The cut plane of mesh.

In OpenFOAM, the detailed model was constructed in the same manner as the MC model, with the only difference being that, for each pin element, the cladding, graphite and other components were homogenized into a single cell without altering the total volume (pin-by-pin). A polyhedral mesh was employed due to its excellent compatibility with complex multi-region geometries, as illustrated in Figure 2. All simulations were conducted at room temperature (293 K), with a vacuum boundary condition applied to the outer surface to maintain consistency with the MC model.

2.2. Governing Equations of Diffusion and SP3 Approximation

The finite volume method, upon which OpenFOAM is based, was used to discretize the solution domain. In this study, two neutronic solvers, with the capacity to only solve mono-region problems, are extended for solving multi-region problems. To describe the neutron behavior, the diffusion equation was first implemented in OpenFOAM. For the multi-region solid-fueled reactor, the used governing equations for neutron flux (φ) and delayed neutron precursors (C , in Eq. (2)) are expressed as follows:

$$\frac{1}{v_g} \frac{\partial \varphi_g}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot D_g \nabla \varphi_g - \Sigma_{t,g} \varphi_g + \sum_{g'=1}^G \Sigma_{s,g'g} \varphi_{g'} + \sum_{i=1}^I \chi_{d,i} \lambda_i C_i + \frac{(1 - \beta_t) \chi_{p,g}}{k_{\text{eff}}} \sum_{g'=1}^G v_{g'} \Sigma_{f,g'} \varphi_{g'}. \quad (1)$$

where the g and i represent the energy and precursor groups, respectively. A unified dynamic formulation is adopted to consistently account for delayed neutron precursors. For critical calculations, time-derivative terms are omitted, and the precursor equations reduce to algebraic relations implicitly included in the effective fission source. The diffusion theory is advantageous in the initial stages of analysis due to its low computational cost. However, for the TRIGA reactor, which features an asymmetric and small-dimension core, the diffusion approximation may not be accurate enough [9]. The Simplified Spherical Harmonics (SP3) approximation provides a more accurate representation of anisotropic effects by solving two neutron moment equations, φ_0 and φ_1 :

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{v_g} \frac{\partial \varphi_{0,g}}{\partial t} = & \nabla \cdot D_g \nabla \varphi_{0,g} + \frac{v_g \Sigma_{f,g} (1 - \beta_t) \chi_{p,g}}{k_{\text{eff}}} \varphi_{0,g} - \Sigma_{r,g} \varphi_{0,g} + \frac{S_{f,g} (1 - \beta_t) \chi_{p,g}}{k_{\text{eff}}} + S_d \chi_{d,g} + S_{s,g} \\ & + 2 \Sigma_{r,g} \varphi_{2,g} + \frac{2}{v_g} \frac{\partial \varphi_{2,g}}{\partial t}; \quad \varphi = \varphi_0 - 2\varphi_2; \quad \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial t} = \frac{\beta_i}{k_{\text{eff}}} \sum_{g'=1}^G v_{g'} \Sigma_{f,g'} \varphi_{g'} - \lambda_i C_i. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{3}{v_g} \frac{\partial \varphi_{2,g}}{\partial t} = & \frac{3}{7} \nabla \cdot \frac{1}{\Sigma_{t,g}} \nabla \varphi_{2,g} - \left(\frac{5}{3} \Sigma_{t,g} + \frac{4}{3} \Sigma_{r,g} \right) \varphi_{2,g} + \frac{2}{3} \Sigma_{r,g} \varphi_{0,g} - \frac{2 v_g \Sigma_{f,g} (1 - \beta_t) \chi_{p,g}}{3 k_{\text{eff}}} \varphi_{0,g} \\ & - \frac{2 S_{f,g} (1 - \beta_t) \chi_{p,g}}{3 k_{\text{eff}}} - \frac{2}{3} S_d \chi_{d,g} - \frac{2}{3} S_{s,g} + \frac{2}{3} \frac{1}{v_g} \frac{\partial \varphi_{0,g}}{\partial t}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Where β_t is total precursor fraction. χ_p and χ_d are prompt and delayed fission neutron spectra, respec-

tively. λ is delay constant. ν is neutron fission yield. $\Sigma_f, \Sigma_r, \Sigma_s, \Sigma_t$ are fission, removal, scattering and total cross-sections, respectively. D is diffusion coefficient. $S_d = \sum_d \lambda_d C_d$, $S_{f,g} = \sum_{g' \neq g} \nu_{g'} \Sigma_{f,g'} \phi_{g'}$ and $S_{s,g} = \sum_{g' \neq g} \Sigma_{s,g'} \phi_{g'}$ are delayed, fission and scattering sources, respectively. v is neutron velocity.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For the validation of the neutronics solver, this work focuses on calibration, control rod worth, and core excess reactivity calculations for the TRIGA Mark II reactor at the University of Pavia, for which experimental data are available and can be found in [8]. Indeed, these quantities can demonstrate their effective predicting range and sensitivity. In this study, all simulations were executed on a computing cluster equipped with Intel® Xeon® E5-2630 v3 CPUs (2.40 GHz) and 64 GB memories, running in parallel mode using 16 cores. The pre-processing stage took approximately 1.19 hours, which involved splitting the multi-region domain and preparing the parallel folders for OpenFOAM. The total simulation times were 1.45 hours for the diffusion method and 1.89 hours for the SP3 method.

3.1. Calibration Curves

The positions of CRs determine their neutron absorption capacity, which is proportional to the reactivity. Hence, it is essential to predict the relationship between the CRs' position and the corresponding reactivity. Reactor reactivity characterizes the reactor critical state $\rho(\text{pcm}) = \frac{k_{\text{eff}} - 1}{k_{\text{eff}}} \times 10^5$, reflecting the balance between neutron production and loss. Thus, a series of simulations was performed in which each CR was withdrawn to different positions (reported in Table I, here 0 m denotes that the CR is fully inserted into the core); then, the corresponding k_{eff} was calculated to determine the associated reactivity. First of all, five different numbers of cells, ranging from 3.34 million to 11.40 million, were adopted to perform the mesh independence analysis. The reactivity decreased with increasing cell number, but the maximum variation was less than 15 pcm. Hence, a mesh with 3.34 million cells was adopted.

Table I. The settings of CR position point

CR	S1 (m)	S2 (m)	S3 (m)	S4 (m)	S5 (m)	S6 (m)	Other positions (m)
REG	0	0.1	0.176	0.252	0.328	0.404	SHIM: 0.196, TRANS: 0.47
SHIM	0	0.1	0.176	0.252	0.328	0.404	SHIM: 0.196, TRANS: 0.47
TRANS	0	0.1	0.1944	0.2888	0.3832	0.4776	REG: 0.196, SHIM: 0.196

As presented in Figures 3 (a), (b) and (c), the relative results were obtained by subtracting the corresponding values at the lowest CR position (S1). Firstly, the MC results show agreement with experimental measurements, with minor discrepancies likely arising from slight inconsistencies in the CR positions between the experimental setup and their representations in OpenMC [8]. In addition, all deterministic results exhibit a trend consistent with both the experimental measurements and MC data under two-energy groups. Regarding the relative results, the SP3 approximation yields better agreement with the MC reference for SHIM; however, the opposite trend appears for both REG and TRANS. In contrast, the absolute results demonstrate that the diffusion method provides better predictive performance than the SP3 approximation, with the exception of the fully inserted cases in both SHIM and TRANS. Quantitatively, for selected positions, the maximum differences between the MC and diffusion results reach 459.81 pcm (12.43%) for REG, 513.67 pcm (23.50%) for SHIM, and 415.04 pcm (13.41%) for TRANS, while the corresponding maximum deviations using the SP3 method are 542.42 pcm (14.67%), 495.52 pcm (11.79%), and 462.68 pcm (13.97%), respectively. Moreover, the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) values of the diffusion method are 170.22 pcm for REG, 170.72 pcm for SHIM and 159.74 pcm for TRANS, whereas the SP3 method yields higher RMSE values of 196.80 pcm, 192.75 pcm and 181.53

pcm, respectively. The underlying reasons primarily lie in the influence of the energy-group structure, in combination with the specific CR's positions. The advantages of the SP3 method may become more evident when a larger number of energy groups is employed, as this enhances inter-group scattering; this aspect will be further investigated in future work. On the other hand, the SP3 generally performs better than the diffusion method in the presence of strong absorbers (i.e., CRs). This explains why the absolute values predicted by SP3 are consistently higher than those from the diffusion method for both SHIM (Figure 3(b)) and TRANS (Figure 3(c)) when the CRs are fully inserted. Such behavior is not observed for REG because its CR reactivity worth is relatively small.

Figure 3. Calibration curves; (a) REG; (b) SHIM; (c) TRANS

3.2. Control Rod Worth

The CR worth represents the maximum capability of a CR to absorb neutrons. It is defined as the difference in reactivity between the states where the CR is fully withdrawn and fully inserted. Accurate prediction of CR worth is essential for evaluating the control range and sensitivity of the CR, which are closely related to reactor power regulation, startup, and shutdown operations. In the experiments, however, the exact positions of the other two CRs were not precisely recorded when evaluating a specific CR. This introduces some uncertainty due to the shadowing effect [8]. To mitigate this issue, the worth of each CR was calculated under the condition with two CRs at their half-withdrawn positions.

Table II. Comparison of control rod worth between experiment measurements and simulations.

CRs	REG (pcm)	SHIM (pcm)	TRANS (pcm)	Excess reactivity (pcm)
Experimental	920.53 ± 50.37	2270.30 ± 131.40	1613.30 ± 240.90	1817.70 ± 21.90
OpenMC	845.85 ± 21.31	2232.58 ± 23.36	1485.58 ± 27.61	1839.33 ± 26.56
Diffusion	789.38	2394.44	1421.79	1872.21
SP3	725.48	2223.83	1389.30	1731.49

As shown in Table II, for the three CRs, the maximum discrepancy between the experimental measurements and MC results is less than 75 pcm, indicating that the CRs' position configuration is reasonable. The differences between the diffusion solver and MC simulations reach 56.47 pcm (6.68%) for the REG, 161.86 pcm (7.25%) for the SHIM, and 63.79 pcm (4.29%) for the TRANS, whereas those for the SP3 solver reach to 120.37 pcm (14.23%), 8.75 pcm (0.39%), and 96.28 pcm (6.48%), respectively. Both solvers demonstrate good performance, as their maximum deviations are rather close to the experimental uncertainty. In addition, the SP3 solver exhibits a greater predictive accuracy than the diffusion solver for SHIM, primarily because of the stronger absorption and the larger reactivity worth of the SHIM rod. However, the diffusion unexpectedly outperforms the SP3 method. This is related to the energy-group structure and the CR positions, which likely affect the inter-group scattering phenomena.

3.3. Core Excess Reactivity

The core excess reactivity refers to the available positive reactivity when all control media (including CRs, poisons) are removed from a critical system. It is an important parameter for evaluating the remaining operational time during which a reactor can sustain a critical state. To calculate this quantity for the TRIGA reactor, the system is first adjusted to achieve criticality, after which all CRs are fully withdrawn. In the critical configuration, the positions of REG, SHIM, and TRANS remain at 0.0027 m, 0.1927 m, and 0.47 m, respectively. The results are summarized in Table II. The MC result is only 21.63 pcm higher than the experimental measurement. Similarly, the core excess reactivities predicted by both solvers show good agreement with both experimental data and MC results, with the discrepancies of 32.88 pcm (1.79%) for the diffusion solver and 107.84 pcm (5.86%) for the SP3 solver.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study verified and validated the diffusion- and SP3-based neutronic solvers for simulation on the complete TRIGA reactor model. OpenMC was employed to generate cross-sections and provide a reference solution. A pin-by-pin geometry, including the surrounding water pool, was constructed in OpenFOAM. To comprehensively evaluate the solvers, calculations of the calibration curves and control rod worths for REG, SHIM, and TRANS, as well as the core excess reactivity, have been performed. The results of both solvers are consistent with experimental measurements and MC simulations, and the RMSE values of the diffusion method are 170.22 pcm for REG, 170.72 pcm for SHIM and 159.74 pcm for TRANS, whereas the SP3 method yields higher values of 196.80 pcm, 192.75 pcm and 181.53 pcm, respectively. Compared to the diffusion method, the advantage of the SP3 approximation to explain the anisotropic effect is only observed in the SHIM rod reactivity worth and at 0 cm position of the calibration curves for both SHIM and TRANS. However, in all other cases, the diffusion method unexpectedly outperforms the SP3 approximation. This is probably due to the influence of the energy-group structure, possibly compounded by the specific CR positions. Nevertheless, the SP3 approximation performs better in predicting SHIM rod reactivity worth, achieving a 6.86% improvement performance at the cost of an additional 0.44 hours of computation. In summary, the two solvers have been verified and validated, while the superiority of the SP3 solver needs to be tested. Its combination with Gaussian

Process Regression (GPR) for cross-section generation is also worth exploring in the future.

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REFERENCES

- [1] C. Fiorina, N. Kerkar, K. Mikityuk, P. Rubiolo, and A. Pautz. "Development and verification of the neutron diffusion solver for the GeN-Foam multi-physics platform." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 96**, pp. 212–222 (2016). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306454916303309>.
- [2] T. Guilbaud, E. Simonnot, A. Scolaro, and C. Fiorina. "Full core study of the KIWI-B-4E Nuclear Thermal Propulsion system using OpenMC and GeN-Foam." *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, **volume 429**, p. 113639 (2024). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0029549324007398>.
- [3] C. Fiorina, M. Hursin, and A. Pautz. "Extension of the GeN-Foam neutronic solver to SP3 analysis and application to the CROCUS experimental reactor." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 101**, pp. 419–428 (2017). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306454916305126>.
- [4] C. Fiorina, M. Aufiero, S. Pelloni, and K. Mikityuk. "A Time-Dependent Solver for Coupled Neutron-Transport Thermal-Mechanics Calculations and Simulation of a Godiva Prompt-Critical Burst." In *Volume 4: Radiation Protection and Nuclear Technology Applications; Fuel Cycle, Radioactive Waste Management and Decommissioning; Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) and Coupled Codes; Reactor Physics and Transport Theory*. American Society of Mechanical Engineers, Prague, Czech Republic (2014).
- [5] Q. Xie, W. Li, C. Guan, Q. Sun, X. Chai, and X. Liu. "Development of 3D transient neutronics and thermal-hydraulics coupling procedure and its application to a fuel pin analysis." *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, **volume 404**, p. 112164 (2023). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0029549323000134>.
- [6] X. Zhou, D. Zhang, L. Zhou, W. Wu, X. Zhang, W. Tian, S. Qiu, and G. Su. "Development and validation of a neutron transport solver with SP3 method based on OpenFOAM." *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, **volume 170**, p. 105120 (2024). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0149197024000702>.
- [7] C. Introini, A. Cammi, S. Lorenzi, F. Giacobbo, et al. "Advanced modelling and stability analysis for nuclear reactors." In *Proceedings of the International Conference Nuclear Energy for New Europe (NENE 2021)*, pp. 1–8. Bled, Slovenia (2021).
- [8] L. Loi, A. Cammi, and C. Introini. "OpenMC Model Validation of the TRIGA Mark II Reactor." In *Proceedings of the 32nd International Conference Nuclear Energy for New Europe (NENE2023)*, pp. 1–8. Portorož, Slovenia (2023).
- [9] Y. Li, J. Qin, F. Xia, and H. Wu. "Fine-mesh homogenization and anisotropic SP3 calculation for PWR cores with plate-type fuel and strong absorbers." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 198**, p. 110283 (2024). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306454923006023>.